

A Critical Study on the ϕ - Scale of Potentials and its Applications to some Electrochemical Problems

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The ϕ —scale of potentials is based on the values of the “null-points” of the metals and can give an indication of the sign and magnitude of the charge on the metal. The scale can, therefore, be applied to any metal, and not only to electrocapillary phenomenon but also to rate of the electrochemical processes involving adsorption, electroreduction or deposition of charged particles. This would, however, be true only, if either surface active substances are considered, or the absolute value of ϕ -potential is sufficiently high to neglect all types of specific interaction between metal and adsorbed species except those of coulombic origin.

The existing methods for determining “null-points” for various metals are unfortunately very inexact and give inconsistent results. This makes it rather difficult for further extension of the ϕ potential concept in the fields of applied electrochemistry—metal deposition, electroorganic reduction and corrosion. Future applications of the ϕ -scale would, however, depend on the accuracy of the determination of the thermionic work function of the metal as well as its potential of electro-capillary maximum.

THE relationship between interfacial tension and applied potential may be represented graphically, forming the so-called parabolic electrocapillary curve (e.c.c.) (Fig. 1). Ostwald¹ proposed an “absolute scale of potentials” with the electrocapillary maximum (e.c.m.) of Hg as the absolute zero potential. The potentials obtained in this way can not be considered absolute in the light of present-day conceptions of electrocapillary phenomena. The potentials of e.c.m. of metals were referred as “null-points of metals²” or “potentials of zero charge (p.z.c.)^{3, 4}”. Antropov⁵ suggested that a distinction should be made between the “null-point of metal², ϵ_N ” and “potential of zero charge $\epsilon_q=0$ ” since the former is made out to be a property of the metal, while the latter is characteristic of the metal/solution system⁶.

The ϕ -scale of Potentials

The “ ϕ -⁷⁻¹⁰ (or correlative¹¹) scale of potentials” is a generalization and development of a somewhat similar concept used for a long time by many workers¹²⁻¹⁴ in the theory of electrocapillarity. In this scale ϵ_N ² has been taken as the basis, and thus values of potential on the “hydrogen scale, ϵ ” expressed in relation to “null-point, ϵ_N ” of the same metal would give the potential in ϕ -scale i.e. $\phi = \epsilon - \epsilon_N$.

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The “rational¹⁵ scale of potential ϕ ” as, $\phi = \epsilon_{nce} - (-0.480)$ where, ϵ_{nce} is the potential of a Hg electrode with respect to the normal calomel electrode, and -0.480 corresponds to the “null-point of Hg” also referred to the normal calomel electrode ; is a special case of Antropov’s ϕ -scale⁷⁻¹⁰ as applied to the Hg electrode only.

The ϕ -scale, representing the charge of a metal with respect to the solution, can also be defined as a “scale of electrode charge” ; this definition would probably better convey the physical meaning of the scale. It can, therefore, give information about the charge of the metal surface (Fig. I : c,d,e), double layer structure (Fig. I : B,C,D), or the most probable electrical nature of particles which are preferentially adsorbed on the electrode surface (Fig. I : x, y, z) under given conditions ; which are of special importance for understanding non-equilibrium electrode processes. It can not, however, handle problems associated with the thermodynamics of electrochemical systems, or with electrode equilibrium ; or enable one to determine direction of a reaction and the e.m.f. of an equilibrium electrochemical system. These can easily be tackled, with the aid of “hydrogen scale, ϵ ”

The applications of ϕ -scale of Potentials

From the nature of ϕ -scale, it would be evident that for any number of metals, their charges and hence, their conditions of physical adsorption are similar

if values of ϕ -potentials of these metals are equal. Moreover, knowing the mechanism of adsorption of surface active substances at least on one metal e.g. on Hg from e.c.c., one can find, by means of the ϕ -scale, the most probable region of potentials in which the same substances can be adsorbed on the surface of any other metal. This allows one to establish in each particular case, the possibility of their influence on the kinetics of the electrochemical reactions. The scale can, therefore, be applied to the kinetics of almost all electrode processes¹⁶, like corrosion inhibition¹⁷⁻²¹, electroreduction, electrodeposition or evolution of gases etc., where adsorption phenomena play a very important role.

The Electrodeposition of Metals :

It can be shown that the values of ϕ -potential and the structure of the electrical double layer are very important factors in the process of metal deposition, and these can suitably interpret the observations of Loshkarev and his coworkers in this field²²⁻²⁵. There are, however, other factors^{26, 27} like surface

film formation, hydrodynamic condition and nature of adsorption, —physical or chemical—, of anions^{28, 29} which also sometimes determine the course of metal electrodeposition ; and these can not be handled by the ϕ -potential theory. Nevertheless, the basis of the scale may be useful in searching for effective additives and electrolytes to be used in plating³⁰⁻³² and in hydroelectrometallurgical baths.

The Electrochemical Reduction and Oxidation :

Adsorption phenomena assume still greater importance in the case of electrolytic reduction and oxidation of organic compounds⁷; and it is then natural to expect the potential to influence the surface concentration of organic compound and, therefore, the rate and the direction of cathodic reaction. This influence is different for various organic substances and metals ; and depends on both the state of the organic compounds³³⁻³⁵ and on the position of the "null-point" of the metal. As regards the role of surface charge in electroreduction, it may be seen in Fig. I that adsorption of surface active cations

Fig. I (i) (A) Solution (s) without surface active (s.a.) addition ;
 (B) the same solution & s.a. organic cations/dipoles ;
 (C) the same solution + s.a. non-ionized organic molecules ;
 (D) the same solution and s.a. organic anions/dipoles.
 (ii) (c) (d) (e): variation of surface charge of Hg from the 'anodic' to the 'cathodic' branch of the e.c.c.(A).
 (iii) Electrical double layers at the solid/solution phase boundary in relation to ϕ -values. x, y, and z denote adsorption of anion, dipole and cation in solution (S) at ϕ_+ , ϕ_0 and ϕ_- potentials respectively on Hg surface.

(B), molecules (C) or anions (D) will take place respectively on the 'negative' branch (e), at the 'maximum' (d) and on the 'positive' branch (c) of the e.c.c., depressing it. It can thus be anticipated that electro-reduction of 'molecular' organic compounds will occur with high efficiency when the 'reduction potential ϵ_R ', of the compound is not very far from the 'null-point' of the electrode used as the cathode for the particular process^{7, 8, 36, 37}; and in many cases it also determines the nature of the end product, sometimes leading to the formation of bimolecular products^{9, 36, 38-41}. The course of the electrochemical redox reaction, therefore, depends not only on the cathodic overpotential but also on the value of the ϕ -potential the former serving as a measure of the reducing or oxidizing action of the electrode, while the latter determining the surface concentration of the depolarizer under given conditions.

The Corrosion Inhibitors :

By 1950, it was quite clear that corrosion inhibition arose as a function of adsorption of inhibitors⁴² and the subsequent effect on the electrode kinetics of one of the component reactions. The work of Iofa^{43, 44} and Antropov⁴⁵ has shown that sign of the charge on the metal surface is important in acidic corrosion. The most extensive development of the theory of relationship between "null-point" of a metal and the functioning of inhibitors by adsorption in acid solution is due to Antropov and his co-workers^{9, 17, 18, 20, 21, 46, 47}.

The well known specific nature of the influence of the same organic compound on the rate of acid corrosion of different metals should at least be partially attributed to the difference in their ϕ -potentials⁴⁸⁻⁵⁰ while if these values for two or more metals are equal, a similar behaviour of the same chemically stable surface active compounds should be expected. This, therefore, led to the determination of the relationship between the electrocapillary data obtained on Hg and the results of corrosion measurements made on Fe possible^{17, 46, 47}, even though Fe having a d-electron bond deficit differs largely from Hg. It is, therefore, reasonable to expect that chemisorption on such metals as Cd and Zn, which from electronic point of view stand closer to Hg, can be evaluated, using the ϕ -scale, from electrocapillary measurements on Hg even more successfully than it was possible to do for Fe. The parallelism between the surface activity of organic compounds on Hg and their inhibition efficiency of acid corrosion manifests itself also in the similar dependence of these two properties on the

structure of organic compounds^{18, 19, 45, 46, 51}. Thus, knowing the corrosion potential of the metal in ϕ -scale, ϕ_c , (Fig. I) one can calculate the "inhibition coefficients K^{**} ", as well as predict which substances would act as corrosion inhibitors^{18, 19}. Besides, the so called synergistic effect of anions and amines in corrosion inhibition of Fe in acid solutions^{52, 52(a), 53} can be satisfactorily explained by the ϕ -potential theory¹⁶.

It should, however, be noted that 'null-point of a metal, ϵ_N ' may be a central quantity, but not the only quantity, in judging the region in which a substance will adsorb upon a metal, and thus inhibit. Other factors like surface structure effect⁵⁴, double layer effect⁵⁵, co-ordination compound formation^{56, 57} and electronic configuration of electrode metals⁵⁸⁻⁶⁰ sometimes appear to play a secondary role as well. It may, in fact, be expected that the action of organic inhibitors chemisorbed on transition metals having incomplete d-orbitals may be different from that developed on non-transitional metals. It should, therefore, be emphasized that the parallel increase of adsorption on Hg and inhibition of Fe corrosion^{18, 19, 46, 61} does not always support the ϕ -potential concept, or a mechanism⁶² in which inhibition is related to attachment of inhibitor molecules to "active centers" on the surface because, (i) maximum inhibition occurs with compounds which have the highest degree of conjugate linking in the molecules⁶³, (ii) inhibiting effects are higher for substances which have smaller free energies of dissolution, and (iii) a favourable inhibition can be one whose cation is adsorbed on the negative branch of the e.c.c., while π -electrons are effective on the positive side. The actual effect of inhibitors depends, besides adsorption, on a series of factors like (i) the electrochemical characteristics of a particular corrosion process, (ii) the nature of the cathodic reaction, (iii) the magnitude and nature of hydrogen overpotential⁴² and (iv) chemical transformations of inhibitors during corrosion⁴⁹ etc. which can not be handled by ϕ -scale of potentials.

The Null-Points of Metals

It has been assumed that adsorption of ions on an electrode surface is possible only when the charge

*The values of K for any organic compound containing nitrogen¹⁸ as $-\text{NH}_2=\text{NH}$, or $\equiv\text{N}$ as the sole active functional group can be estimated from relevant e.c. curves alone. This technique has been confirmed with mono-, and poly hydric alcohols, phenols and its derivatives and thioureas (B. R. Guha, Burdwan University Ph.D. Thesis, in preparation, private communication.)

of that surface has a sign opposite to that of the ion. This leads to discrepancies between the calculated and experimentally derived p.z.c.^{20, 64, 65}. This may be due to the effect of the nature of a charged surface and its surrounding solution, as well as the interaction between an ion and such a surface. It is possible that adsorption will already begin to take place, while the sign of the surface charge is still the same as that of the adsorbed ion^{15, 66}. The use of the p.z.c. as calculated by Antropov²⁰ from work function⁵⁵ as the criterion for the onset of adsorption is also not sufficient; the properties of the ions have to be taken into account as well.

There is no sufficient certainty, except for Hg, that values listed in literature^{5, 10, 16} are really null-points of the metals and not their p.z.c. This arises from the fact that ions which are not surface active at the Hg-water interface are capable of being specifically adsorbed on the surfaces of other metals. Moreover, it can not be stated with a sufficient degree of certainty that null-points calculated theoretically corresponds, both in physical meaning and in magnitude, to the experimental null-point as data for both the potential of e.c.m. and the thermionic work function is unreliable with solid metals as both these quantities are extremely sensitive to the presence of traces of impurities⁶⁷. It can, however, be possible to calculate the null-points of metals with an accuracy close to that provided by most direct measurements (+0.1 v) which is quite sufficient even for quantitative treatment of the problems mentioned above, though the error involved in the value of the null-point will be more significant as regards inferences relating adsorption of charged species. It is possible that null-point of a metal may have more than one value depending on the actual state of the metal^{10, 67} and in such a case the value of null-point should be taken with respect to actual state of the electrode.

Conclusion

Though Antropov's hypotheses on ϕ -scale of potentials are of theoretical importance, an extension of its application in electrochemical kinetics⁶⁸ would depend on the accuracy of the determination of the electronic work function of the metal. One can, however, strongly advocate the use of the ϕ -(or correlative or reduced) scale of potentials" in its present form when interpreting phenomena involving adsorption, electro-reduction or deposition of charged particles.

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S. N. BANERJEE : A CRITICAL STUDY OF THE ϕ - SCALE OF POTENTIALS

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